

DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8360685>

Abstract. *This article provides information about the current state of the methodology for developing the information competence of future primary school teachers in the conditions of digitalization and the didactic possibilities of developing the information competence of the future primary school teachers in the digitalization environment.*

Keywords: *digitization, professional communication, Internet, information, audiovisual materials, professional activity.*

In the conditions of new digitization conditions all existing higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, the need for improving the methodology of teaching the subject of information technologies in future primary school teachers is increasing day by day. In this regard, the importance of students in education through training with the medium of ICT, their professional functions in the labor market as a whole, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to the development of professional communicative competencies. The educational policy, quality and opportunities of professional activity of each higher educational institution should be socially protected, adapted to constantly changing conditions and aimed at solving the training of professional communicative competence developed, competitive specialists.

In current situations, in the conditions of digitization to students of a higher educational institution, the purpose and task of improving the methodology for teaching the science of collaborative technologies in future primary class teachers is to develop professional communicative competence of students. To do this, it is very important to effectively implement the goal (mission) and tasks of world-class study of foreign languages in each higher educational institution through the means of information and communication technologies.

In the context of digitization, the future primary school teachers were characterized by the rapid development of research in areas where it was possible to improve the methodology of teaching the science of information technologies. Later one of the many Uzbek scientists R.J. Ishmuhamedov suggested that in primary classes, it is better to perform the duties of consultants, partners and use information-communication technologies for educational purposes.

Thus, in the context of digitalization, we can see that it is effective for future primary school teachers to improve the methodology of teaching information technology, to develop programs, training and testing programs to support the use of information-communication technologies for teaching in the primary class, to develop computer courses, distance learning, to use the internet in auditoriums.

In the context of digitalization, the future primary school teachers is the most suitable effective tool in improving the methodology for teaching Information Technology, the purpose of which is the development of professional communication of students. It is desirable that interest in the use of information-communication technologies in teaching in primary classes is widely

introduced in all higher education institutions. This is confirmed by the fact that the global network of the internet allows teachers to solve many problems in the field of development of professional communicative skills.

In the context of digitalization, the ability to improve the methodology of teaching Information Technology in future primary school teachers, develop research activities and seek information; is the most effective means of developing communication skills. This is especially true of the fact that it concerns the communication capabilities of the internet for the solution of specific educational tasks, the development and improvement of certain educational skills and qualifications, the organization of educational communications as X. Gulyamova insists. In this regard, it is important to develop such issues as communication in the study and teaching of foreign languages, methods of obtaining information and audiovisual materials from the internet network, the use of information and communication technologies in the study of various disciplines.

It is necessary that the teacher tries to have the characteristics of five information competencies. In the work activities of some teachers, we see that the competency characteristics in question are of a sufficiently high level (high professional training and good results in teaching students, the personality of the teacher fully manifests itself, pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication shows him as a competent teacher).

In this regard, researchers consider teacher competence to be a professionally trained quality, indicating that a teacher's professional competence must include at least professional knowledge, professional skill, and professionally significant personal characteristics. At the same time, some researchers noted that the teacher has general and special knowledge, others - to master professional qualifications, more others - to acquire certain psychological characteristics, the necessary knowledge and qualifications, and fourth-party scientists - to become a professionally competent teacher, personal characteristics are important.

Teaching information technologies to the future primary class teachers in the context of digitalization, it is determined by the Bologna Process, which studies the indicators of the quality of professional education on the basis of improving the methodology of teaching Information Technology.

In the content of the modernization of education, it is obvious to understand professional competence as an integral indicator of the quality of training of the future teacher, which is not determined through a certain set of knowledge and skills, but represents the skills of a person to carry out the knowledge and experiences acquired in a specific situation. The professional skills of the teacher include various competencies, including information competence.

In modern conditions, it is known that the informational competence of a teacher determines his/her professional pedagogical competence in general.

In conditions of informatization of education, the teacher must know the use of new information-communicative technologies in it in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Ye.V. Ivanova views the information competence of a teacher as a special type of organization of knowledge related to a special subject that allows effective decisions in professional-pedagogical activity, as an organizational part of the professional competence of the teacher, which includes the following organizers of professional activity, these are:

theoretical knowledge of basic concepts and methods of informatics as a scientific discipline;

methods of presentation, storage, processing and transmission of information using a computer;

skills and qualifications of working on a personal computer based on the use of operating systems, utilities, settings in operating systems and electron shells;

the ability to express information on the Internet;

the skills of organizing independent work of learners using internet technologies;

ownership of the qualifications for the use of telecommunication technologies, taking into account its specificity in a particular discipline.

In this sense, the author associates the information competence of the teacher only with computer literacy and the skill of using new information and communication technologies in the educational process.

Thus, the researcher states that the information-communicative competencies that form a system in this list are considered, since they are the basis of information activity (the main manifestation of activity in an information society), which provides for the finding, Assessment and use of the necessary information in professional pedagogical activity.

According to the authors, at the stage of communication with learners, the information skills of the teacher are manifested in the following abilities:

an understandable and clear description of the educational material, taking into account the specificity of subject, the level of training of students, their life experiences and ages;

logically correct construction and conduct of a specific story, explanation, conversation, problematic statement;

harmoniously combine the use of inductive and deductive ways of stating the material;

formation of questions in an understandable form, short, clear and expressive way;

application of technical means of exhibitionism in teaching: expression of thought using graphics, diagrams, schemes, images;

rapid delivery of character and level by students to master new material using different methods;

restructure the plan and course of the statement of the material if necessary.

As concepts that shape and clarify the informational competence of the future primary school teacher, the author distinguishes:

algorithmic literacy – a set of special outlines, skills and qualifications associated with the acquisition of common components of algorithmization;

computer literacy - mastering the initial skills of communication with PC and office equipment, familiarization with basic software;

informational literacy - the skill of creating, processing, storing and using information on the computer networks of the necessary, including communication;

user based and technological literacy - information systems are stable competencies in the use of packages of applied applications in their field of subject (word processors, spreadsheets, database, semantic networks, expert systems, automated design systems, Internet, etc.), the skill of literate preparation of articles and presentations;

the image of informative behavior, a set of behaviors carried out to obtain, process and assimilate existing information, create new knowledge and communicate it to the professional community;

computerized communication is the purposeful interaction of subjects and objects of communication, aimed at regulating all spheres of social life in order to maintain the uniqueness and integrity of a person, filling the place of limited human capabilities.

N.V. Kisel understands a special type of organization of knowledge related to a special discipline that allows the teacher to adopt effective solutions in professional pedagogical activity under the competence of information and indicates the degree of acquisition and use of Information Technology in the educational process.

At this point, improving the methodology for teaching information technology to future primary school teachers in the conditions of digitalization, can be manifested, that is, deep personal interest in this type of activity. Therefore, in addition to the organizers of cognitive (knowledge) and operational-technological (skills, experience), information competence provides for the existence of internal motivation for the qualitative implementation of information activities in an individual, a valuable attitude to this activity.

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